

EFFECT OF LAYUP AND PLY MORPHOLOGY ON VOID FORMATION IN OUT-OF-AUTOCLAVE PREPREGS

T. Centea¹, M. Préau¹ and P. Hubert^{1,*}

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, McGill University, Montreal, Canada

* Corresponding author (pascal.hubert@mcgill.ca)

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1 Introduction

Out-of-autoclave (OOA) prepregs are intended for vacuum-bag-only (VBO) manufacturing of high performance parts in an unpressurized oven. Since the maximum available consolidation pressure differential is about 101 325 Pa (or 1 atm), the defect suppression capacity of the OOA/VBO process is significantly reduced relative to the benchmark autoclave approach.

To limit the potential for void formation, OOA prepregs typically feature a partially impregnated microstructure consisting of dry fibre tow cores and surrounding resin rich areas. The dry areas allow gases to evacuate in the early stages of processing. Then, they are infiltrated by surrounding resin [1].

The effectiveness of introducing porous areas in prepregs to ensure low porosity in the final part has been previously demonstrated [2,3], and recently, OOA prepregs have been used to produce low defect parts in a variety of contexts (for example, [4,5]). However, studies have also shown that the consolidation of such prepregs (which involves air evacuation, fibre bed compaction, resin flow and the formation of flow- or gas-induced voids) is highly sensitive. Indeed, factors such as resin moisture absorption [6-8], cure cycle [9,10], out-time [9,11,12], vacuum quality [8,13], and fibre bed architecture [9,10,13] have been shown to induce porosity. Thus, while OOA/VBO oven cure is a viable alternative to the autoclave, the allowable material and process windows must be understood in order to avoid significant quality reductions.

Despite the above-mentioned studies, the effect of several variables remains unknown. Among them, the possible effect of multiple reinforcement types

within a single laminate is particularly relevant, since the large, complex parts for which OOA processing is ostensibly well-suited are likely to be built up of different prepregs. A further point of interest is the coupling of different process deficiencies. Indeed, while factors such as out-time and pressure have been studied separately, they are likely to be encountered simultaneously.

2 Objectives and structure

The present study considered the consolidation of “hybrid” OOA laminates in a variety of situations. First, laminates based on two commercially-available prepregs with different fibre bed architectures were manufactured under both ideal and deficient material and process conditions. Then, samples were analyzed using optical microscopy and X-ray micro-tomography (micro-CT) to determine the amount, distribution and morphology of porosity.

3 Materials

The two OOA prepregs used within this study were manufactured by Cytec Engineered Materials from 5320 epoxy resin and two carbon fibre beds: a plain-weave fabric (T650-35 PW, 196 g/m² areal weight, 36 % wt resin content) and a unidirectional tape (T40/800B, 145 g/m² areal weight, 33 % wt resin content). Both prepregs were imaged uncured using a previously proposed micro-CT method [1], and representative x-ray micrographs are shown in Fig. 1. By convention, denser areas appear in brighter grey while voids are black. Both prepregs feature a partially impregnated microstructure containing both dry fibre tow cores and resin-rich areas. In addition, the PW fabric-based laminate also includes large macro-pores between its plies, which represent air entrapped during layup.

Fig. 1. X-ray micrographs of unprocessed 5320/PW (top) and 5320/UD (bottom) laminates. The bright grey areas are resin-rich areas, while the darker areas are dry, micro-porous fibre tow cores.

4 Methods and procedures

4.1 Laminate manufacture

Laminates were vacuum-bag cured in a convection oven, within a fixture capable of controlling bag and ambient pressures independently. The fixture, shown in Fig. 2, consists of a flat tool plate (on which the vacuum bag is placed) and a lid (which covers and seals the entire assembly). The bag and lid volumes are connected to independent vacuum systems, which can vary the pressure between 0 atm and 1 atm. Thus, the pressure “ambient” to the bag, and therefore the consolidation pressure, can be controlled while maintaining full vacuum in the bag. The entire fixture can also be placed in a convection oven for controlled heating.

Twelve laminates were manufactured within the fixture using three layups, three out-times, and two ambient pressures, as shown in Table 1.

Fig. 2. Schematic of the consolidation fixture.

Table 1. Laminate layup and manufacturing conditions.

#	Layups	Out-Times	Ambient Pressures
1	[PW0°/UD0°/PW0°/UD0°] _s	4 days	1 atm
2	[PW45°/UD0°/PW-45°/UD0°] _s	4 days	1 atm
3	[PW0°/UD0°/UD90°/PW45°] _s	4 days	1 atm
4	[PW0°/UD0°/PW0°/UD0°] _s	4 days	0.775 atm
5	[PW45°/UD0°/PW-45°/UD0°] _s	4 days	0.775 atm
6	[PW0°/UD0°/UD90°/PW45°] _s	4 days	0.775 atm
7	[PW0°/UD0°/PW0°/UD0°] _s	19 days	0.775 atm
8	[PW45°/UD0°/PW-45°/UD0°] _s	19 days	0.775 atm
9	[PW0°/UD0°/UD90°/PW45°] _s	19 days	0.775 atm
10	[PW0°/UD0°/PW0°/UD0°] _s	25 days	0.775 atm
11	[PW45°/UD0°/PW-45°/UD0°] _s	25 days	0.775 atm
12	[PW0°/UD0°/UD90°/PW45°] _s	25 days	0.775 atm

The three layups vary ply orientations as well as the number of PW/UD interfaces. The out-times span (and exceed) the resin out-life of 21 days, and the ambient pressures bound the range that may reasonably be encountered. The bag pressure was constant and nominally vacuum, as required by VBO processing. Together, these twelve laminates expand on previous experiments in the literature by combining possible causes of flow-induced voids (out-time) and gas-induced voids (reduced pressure). All laminates were cured using a four hour room temperature vacuum hold, a ramp of 0.65 °C/min ± 0.15 °C/min to 93 °C and an eight hour hold at 93 °C. The vacuum bag arrangement consisted of a non-perforated release film on the tool; the laminate; another non-perforated release film; edge breathing dams (made of sealant tape wrapped in dry fiberglass boat cloth) around the laminate perimeter; one layer of breather, and the vacuum bag. Type-K thermocouples were placed in the oven air, on the tool and on the laminate surface for monitoring.

4.2 Laminate quality analysis

4.2.1 Optical microscopy

Three samples measuring approximately 50 mm by 25 mm were sectioned from each cured laminate, and their edges were polished with up to 1200 grit sandpaper on a Buehler MetaServ Grinder/Polisher for through-thickness optical micrographs. These

micrographs served to qualitative assess the laminate microstructure, and to validate the more detailed observations and analysis made using micro-CT.

4.2.1 Micro-CT

Samples measuring 18 x 25 mm were sectioned from the center of each cured laminate and scanned in a Skyscan 1172 High Resolution micro-CT, at a pixel size of 5.44 µm/pixel; an image size of 4000 by 2096 pixels; a source voltage and intensity of 40 kV and 250 µA, respectively, and with no filter. The results were then reconstructed into sets of parallel x-ray micrographs, oriented both in the plane of lamination and in the through-thickness direction (as shown in Fig 3). Exceptionally, for laminate 12, two

Fig. 3. Schematic of micro-CT sample showing through-thickness and in-plane micrograph planes.

Fig. 4. Cure cycle temperature profile.

samples scanned in different orientations were deemed necessary, as some fine porosity was difficult to detect for a single sample orientation (as discussed in section 5.3.2.2).

The through-thickness micrographs and Skyscan's CTan software were used to calculate the laminate porosity. First, a region of interest tightly enclosing the laminate interior (but no edges damaged by sample cutting) was defined. Then, the micrographs were converted from grayscale to binary images through a consistent threshold value. Finally, CTan's 3D analysis feature was used to compute the percent

solid and void volume. In addition, for high-porosity laminates, the approximate porosity in each individual layer was also determined by applying the above procedure to local regions of interest. For sample 12, data from both scans was merged.

5 Results and discussion

5.1 Laminate manufacture

The temperature profile common to all cured laminates is shown in Fig. 4. The oven temperature features an over-compensation at the end of the ramp, designed to ensure the desired laminate heat-up rate. The tool- and bag-side readings, which overlap almost perfectly, show that there were no significant through-thickness thermal gradients.

5.2 Optical microscopy

Fig. 5 shows representative optical micrograph sections of laminates 1 and 10; both had the same layup, but the former was processed under ideal conditions while the latter was exposed to 25 days of out-time and cured under reduced ambient pressure. These process differences were highly detrimental to laminate quality. Indeed, while laminate 1 features a uniform and largely void-free microstructure, laminate 10 contains significant porosity in the central regions of the fibre-dense tows, in both the PW and UD layers. These dry areas are likely flow-induced voids brought on by out-time, increased resin viscosity and incomplete tow impregnation

Fig. 5. Optical micrograph sections of laminate 1 (top) and laminate 10 (bottom), with insets. Laminate 1 shows no notable micro- and macro-porosity, while laminate 10 shows significant and pervasive micro-porosity within the fibre-dense tows.

[9-11]. Interestingly, despite the reduced consolidation pressure, laminate 10 does not exhibit any significant macro-porosity between the plies or in resin-rich regions.

Similar optical cross-sections were obtained for all manufactured laminates. Generally, laminates 1 to 9 contained no notable porosity, while laminates 10 to 12 exhibited significant dry fibre areas.

5.3 Micro-CT

5.3.1 Representative X-Ray micrographs

Fig. 6 shows representative sections of through-thickness optical and x-ray micrographs (though not of the exact same region) for a laminate with no porosity (laminate 1) and significant porosity (laminate 10).

The x-ray micrographs confirm the previous results by showing differing levels of quality. Whereas laminate 1 has a uniform, void-free microstructure laminate 10 shows pervasive porosity in the form of numerous “darker” regions. The general appearance of these regions is similar to the dry areas observed in Fig. 1 for both prepregs; thus, as explained before, they are likely fibre tow cores that have remained un-infiltrated due to increases in resin viscosity induced by out-time [9-11]. Furthermore, it is again interesting to note the absence of bubble-like, gas-induced macro-porosity.

Overall, these micrographs confirm the local observations made using optical microscopy: laminates 1 to 9 had no notable porosity, while laminates 10 to 12 contained extensive dry fibre areas. However, no patterns in the shape and distribution of the pores are immediately obvious.

Fig. 7 shows laminate 10’s microstructure through three in-plane micrographs taken at different points: within one external PW0° layer, at the interface of the latter and the adjacent UD0° layer, and within the UD0° layer. From this perspective, a pattern in the shape and distribution of the porosity becomes apparent.

Laminate 1

Layup: [PW0°/UD0°/PW0°/UD0°]_s
Out-time: 4 days
Ambient Pressure: 1 atm

Laminate 10

Layup: [PW0°/UD0°/PW0°/UD0°]_s
Out-time: 25 days
Ambient Pressure: 0.775 atm

← 2 mm →

Fig. 6. Representative sections of optical and in-plane x-ray micrographs for laminate 1 (top) and laminate 10 (bottom) Note that the micrographs do not show the exact same region. Laminate 1, manufactured under ideal conditions, shows a void-free microstructure. Laminate 10, manufactured at high out-time and under deficient pressure, shows pervasive porosity.

PW layer

UD layer (next to PW layer)

UD layer (center of layer)

Fig. 7. Aligned in-plane x-ray micrographs of laminate 10 showing PW and UD porosity patterns.

Within the PW fabric layer, the porosity is located within the center of each tow, as expected in the case of flow-induced dry areas. Within the adjacent UD layer, close to the PW/UD interface, the dry areas of the unidirectional fibre bed are located over the PW fabric's resin-rich regions, or over the edges of each fabric tow's "unit cell" (or repeating unit). Finally, at the center of the UD layer, the dry areas are pervasive and more evenly distributed, and the porosity pattern corresponding to the PW layer's morphology is no longer dominant. These observations indicate that, to some extent, the adjacent PW and UD layers in laminate 10 interact during consolidation. Specifically, they suggest that the distinctive fabric morphology of the PW, made

PW layer

UD layer

PW layer

Fig. 8. Aligned in-plane x-ray micrographs of laminate 11 showing PW and UD porosity patterns.

up of raised overlapping tows and recessed, regularly spaced resin-rich areas, affects the consolidation of the UD ply by applying an uneven pressure on it. The raised overlapping tow regions are likely to apply a relatively high pressure, and correspond to low-porosity regions; conversely, the recessed inter-tow regions seem associated to high porosity-regions. Fig. 8 shows a similar set of in-plane micrographs from laminate 11, in which a UD 0° ply is set between two PW 45° layers. Within both PW plies, micro-porosity is located inside the fibre tow cores. Within the UD ply, significant porosity is visible, as before, in a pattern defined by the resin-rich, inter-tow areas of the fabric (in this case, these zones are offset by 45°).

Fig. 9. Laminate (bulk) void content versus layup, out-time and processing pressure.

5.3.2 Porosity

5.3.2.1 Laminate porosity

The volumetric laminate porosity data obtained for each manufactured part through 3D micro-CT analysis is shown in Fig. 9.

The laminates manufactured under 4 and 19 days of out-time are found to be of very high quality, with void contents consistently below 0.5 % regardless of ambient pressure. These low porosity values render any firm conclusion about the effect of layup difficult. However, they highlight the robustness of the materials under study. Indeed, these OOA prepregs produced void contents well below the 1 – 2 % limit commonly used for high performance parts, even when close to their out-life (21 days) and under a 20 % ambient pressure reduction.

In previous work, micro-porosity has been mainly associated with out-time, while macro-voids have mostly been associated to reduced pressure [13]. Remarkably, laminates 1 to 9 present neither such defect in notable quantities. In particular, the lack of macro-porosity is likely related to the four hour room temperature vacuum hold used to evacuate entrapped air, and thus to limit void nucleation sites.

Altogether, the quality of laminates 1 to 9 suggests that if sufficient air is evacuated, high quality parts may be produced even when subject to simultaneous process deficiencies.

Laminates 10 to 12, manufactured under 25 days of out-time, present significantly higher void content levels, ranging from close to 4 % for laminates 10 and 11 to 3 % for laminate 12. Since these values correspond to single data points obtained from small-scale samples, they should be considered approximate. However, several inferences may still be drawn. The considerable void content increases in all three laminates relative to the previous cases confirms that, as suggested in previous studies, out-time strongly impedes prepreg impregnation during processing and lead to pervasive dry fibre areas [9-11]. However, the approx. 0.62% decrease in laminate 12 suggests the possible influence of layup.

Laminates 10, 11 and 12 contain the same number of PW and UD layers, negating the influence of an individual prepreg's behaviour. Furthermore, the similar void contents displayed by laminates 10 and 11 in spite of different layer orientations suggest that the relative angle between PW and UD plies may not be the dominant parameter. The main difference between laminates 10 and 11 and laminate 12 is the

stacking sequence. The former two layups alternate fabric and tape, and feature six interfaces between PW and UD plies. Conversely, the latter layup groups UD layers, and features only four such interfaces. This decrease in interfaces, and thus of uneven pressure application on the UD plies, is therefore a possible cause of the decreased void content observed in laminate 12.

5.3.2.2 Layer porosity

Fig. 10 shows the layer porosity distribution for laminates 10 to 12, which contain noticeable porosity. As previously mentioned, for laminate 12, the data for the UD0° plies was obtained from a second micro-CT scan, as it was observed that, in the initial scan, the finely-grained micro-porosity in those layers was not captured with the same contrast and fidelity as that in the PW0°, PW45° and UD0° layers. This limitation is likely due to a combination of chosen scan resolution (whose pixel size is roughly equivalent to the inter-fibre spacing), sample orientation during scanning (which, in this case, may have favored the UD90° cross-sections) and noise in the scan and reconstruction steps.

Several trends common to the three laminates may be noted. The porosity is remarkably symmetric around the laminate mid-plane, suggesting that the porosity-generating mechanisms depending on intra-ply rather than inter-ply or laminate properties; this result supports the hypothesis that the measured porosity is flow-induced and, more specifically, due to incomplete tow impregnation within each ply. Furthermore, in the majority of cases, the porosity contribution of the UD plies is higher than that of the PW layers. This difference suggests that the UD plies are more difficult to impregnate than their PW counterparts, either due to a lower initial degree of impregnation or a slower resin infiltration velocity (due, for example, to fibre-denser tows, thicker fibres and/or a lower transverse permeability).

7 Conclusions

The present study considered the effect of hybrid laminate layup and coupled process deficiencies on consolidation in OOA/VBO prepreg processing. Laminates comprised of both fabric and unidirectional tape plies were manufactured in ideal

and high out-time, reduced ambient pressure conditions.

Fig. 10. Layer porosity distribution for laminates 10, 11 and 12.

Then, they were analyzed using micro-CT and optical microscopy.

The results showed that high quality, low-porosity laminates may be manufactured even under significant out-time and reduced pressure if the

material's out-life is not exceeded. In cases of excessive out-life, significant porosity was observed for all hybrid layups. However, a limited but noticeable reduction in porosity may have been obtained by decreasing the number of fabric/tape ply interfaces.

These results are relevant to fundamental processing science: for hybrid laminates, the idea of stacking sequence as a possible cause of defects contributes to the understanding of void formation mechanisms, offers further focal points for the analysis of OOA prepreg consolidation. More broadly, it also suggests that consolidation should be studied locally as well as at the laminate scale. These results are also relevant to the applied use of OOA/VBO materials, though perhaps in a different way. Although a possible link between layup and porosity was observed, its influence was only felt in laminates with unacceptably high defect levels. Conversely, in laminates with acceptable porosity levels, the influence of layup was negligible. Thus, from an application standpoint, these results highlight that high quality OOA prepreg parts built up from multiple fibre bed architectures may be manufactured without needing to consider the influence of layup.

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